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& the environment

Department:
Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment
REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

CRUISE REPORT

Benguela Air-Sea CO₂ and Heat Flux Experiment (Benflex)

Southern Benguela Current Region
South-East Atlantic Ocean
6 – 19 December 2021

NUI Galway
OÉ Gaillimh

SEA
TECHNOLOGY
SERVICES

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1. TITLE: Benguela Air-Sea CO₂ and Heat Flux Experiment

Ship's name: RV *ALGOA*

Voyage number: VOYAGE 278 (ALG278)

Area of operation: West Coast of South Africa along the St. Helena Bay monitoring line (SHBML)

Port of departure (City, Country): Cape Town, South Africa

Port of entry (City, Country): Cape Town, South Africa

Quarantine (COVID-19): 28 November 2021 - 06 December 2021

Quarantine Hotel: The Capital Mirage Hotel

Departure Date: 06 December 2021

Return Date: 19 December 2021

Principal Investigators

Mr. Mutshutshu Tsanwani (Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment, South Africa, mtsanwani@dffe.gov.za)

Dr Pedro. M.S. Monteiro (Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, South Africa, PMonteir@csir.co.za)

Dr Brian Ward (National University of Ireland, Galway, bward@nuigalway.ie)

Dr Sebastiaan Swart (Gothenburg University, Sweden, sebastiaan.swart@marine.gu.se)

Dr Sarah Nicholson (Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, South Africa, sarahanne.n@gmail.com)

Dr Marcel du Plessis (Gothenburg University, Sweden, marcel.du.plessis@gu.se)

Mr. Christo Whittle (Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, South Africa, Christo.whittle@gmail.com)

Mr Mduduzi Seakamela (Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment, South Africa, smseakamela@dffe.gov.za)

3. Participants

Title Name and Surname	Institution / Affiliation	Responsibility
1. Mutshutshu Tsanwani♂ ⁺	DFFE	Chief Scientist/ DIC, TA, and underway pCO ₂ measurements
2. Thato Mtshali♂	DFFE	Biogeochemistry group leader and DIC, DO, CHL, Nutrients sample collection
3. Gavin Tutt♂	DFFE	Conductivity Temperature and Depth (CTD) instrument operator and monitoring ADCP and TSG

4. Baxolele Mdokwana♂	DFFE	pCO ₂ system monitoring, and DIC, DO, CHL, Nutrients sample collection
5. Chris Jabulani♂	DEFF	DIC, DO, CHL, Nutrients sample collection
6. Gianluca Gerich♂	GU	Monitored the Thermosalinograph (TSG), TSG data analysis, and DIC, DO, CHL, Nutrients sample collection
7. Christo Whittle♂	CSIR	Monitored Infrared Sea Surface Temperature Autonomous Radiometer (ISAR)
8. Joshua Huysamen♂	STS	To monitor all sensor on the Flux Tower
9. Steven McCue♂	DFFE	Conducted Top predator population including Seabirds, whales, dolphins, seals, etc.
10. Sinalo Mswane♀	DFFE	Provided Electronics/Engineering support and assisted with CTD and underway sampling

Notes and Abbreviations: ♂ denotes Male and ♀ denotes Female

4. Scientific Equipment

- Underway partial pressure of carbon dioxide (pCO₂) system for surface pCO₂ measurements - (DEFF: Mutshutshu Tsanwani)
- Conductivity, Temperature and Depth (CTDO)/Rossette sampler for depth profiling of conductivity (salinity), temperature, Fluorescence, Density and oxygen concentrations, and Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) - (DEFF: Gavin Tutt)
- Infrared Sea Surface Temperature Autonomous Radiometer (ISAR)- (CSIR: Christo Whittle)
- Heat Flux sensors - (Sea Technology Services: Joshua Huysamen)
- Surface vehicle (SV3)-Wave Glider and Slocum – (CSIR: Sarah Nicholson)
- Titrino for Winkler titration – (DEFF: Thato Mtshali)
- Surface vehicle (SV3)-Wave Glider and Slocum - (CSIR: Sarah Nicholson)

5. Introduction

The ocean plays a vital role in regulating atmospheric carbon dioxide. Roughly, 23% of anthropogenic carbon dioxide emissions have been taken up the ocean in the past six decades (Engelbrecht and Monteiro, 2021). Accurate estimates of air-sea carbon dioxide flux are crucial to forecast climate change, to predict and quantify potential effects of changes in the chemistry of sea water on marine ecosystems, and in

developing mitigation measures. The Benguela Air-Sea CO₂ and Heat Flux Experiment (Benflex21) was initially planned to take place onboard the SA Agulhas II polar research ship but for technical reasons, that was not possible. The experiment was then replanned to take place in the southern Benguela Upwelling System (sBUS) on a long-term observational line in St Helena Bay (Fig 1).

The aims of the experiment were to examine, through top-down eddy co-variance and bottom-up in situ ocean observations, the hypothesis that small differences between the skin, foundation, and bulk temperatures are causing an underestimation of the air-sea flux of CO₂ that can influence the magnitude of the global ocean sink (Watson et al., 2020; 1992; Woolf et al., 2017).

6. Objectives

1. To examine, using high-resolution Eddy Co-Variance (EcV) and in situ observations, the role of the ocean “cool skin” on the air-sea flux of CO₂ and heat
2. To examine, through high-resolution observations, the impact of the vertical temperature gradient in the upper 10m of the water column on the estimation of the air-sea flux
3. To examine the sensitivity of 1 and 2 under a wide range of diurnal and synoptic wind stress and surface layer mixing conditions
4. To link the variability in the temperature gradients and p CO₂ to mixed layer dynamics in response to the interaction of wind-linked mixing and heat-linked stratification.
5. To understand the synoptic scale variability of the CO₂ and heat fluxes
6. To understand how synoptic scale influence diurnal variability of DIC and TA
7. To investigate how representative the bulk heat flux parameterisations are to the true EcV heat fluxes, particularly over sharp lateral temperature gradients
8. To determine the respective role of fine-scale lateral oceanic processes (submesoscales) and synoptic atmospheric variability to the leading order variability of surface heat fluxes.
9. To conduct Top predator population including Seabirds, whales, dolphins, seals, etc.

7. Research Area

The RV *Algoa* occupied a station on the west coast of South Africa at LAT: 39.39° S and LON: 17.90° E between station 4 and 5 of the St Helena Bay monitoring transect on the 6th to the 18th of December 2021. The station was continuously occupied with the ship's position facing into the wind to provide the Eddy Co-Variance with an unobstructed flow of air.

Figure 1. The study area for the Benflex cruise indicating a station occupied between 4 and 5 along the SHBML. The plot on the right shows that Wave glider bowtie track represented in blue. The brown dots represent locations where cross calibration of the Slocum glider with sensors on the vessel was done.

5. CTD Operators/Physics Report.

(Compiled by Gavin Tutt, Gianluca Gerich)

Responsible Operator's Name: Gavin Tutt

5.1. CTD

CTD casts were done every 3 hours, starting at 06:00 and ending at 21:00 at a single location (39.39° S and 17.90° E). A total of 62 CTD casts were successfully completed. Seawater samples were collected at 06:00 am and 18:00 pm CTD casts for the following parameters (Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC), Total Alkalinity (TA), Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Nutrients, and Chlorophyll *a* (*Chl-a*)). The other CTD casts were completed for the profile only and were used to calibrate the wave glider. On one occasion the CTD cable hopped off the sheave. The CTD sensors (Table 5.1) were flushed with fresh water after every cast and with Triton-x every third day. On completion of the cruise the CTD unit was washed down with fresh water and the sensors flushed with Triton-x.

Table 5.1: CTD Sensor List (Type, Model, serial number, calibration date, Stations used)

Instrument/sensor	Mfr./Model	Serial Number	Calibration Date	Stations Used
Deck Unit	Sea-Bird SBE11	18621	n/a	001-062
Carousel Water Sampler	Sea-Bird SBE32(12-PI.)		n/a	001-062
CTD	Sea-Bird SBE9plus		23/02/2021	001-062
Pressure	Digiquartz with TC	0746	19/03/2021	001-062
Primary Temperature	Sea-Bird SBE3plus	4136	23/02/2021	001-062
Primary Conductivity	Sea-Bird SBE4C	3811	23/03/2021	001-062
Dissolved Oxygen	Sea-Bird SBE43	1422	23/03/2021	001-062
Primary Pump	Sea-Bird SBE5T			001-062
Fluorometer	Wetlab ECO-AFL/FI	FLTRD-2053	03/09/2021	001-062
PAR	Biospherical QSP-2300	70168	11/04/2021	001-062
Altimeter	Benthos PSA-916D	69212	24/05/2021	001-062

5.2. Challenges

The only issue found with regards to the CTD was that niskin bottle # 9 failed to close on most of the casts where sampling was done.

5.3. CTD Station details

Station	Grid	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Time (hh:mm)	Latitude (°S)	Longitude (°E)	Sounding (db)	Deployment Depth (db)
C13627	CTD001	07/12/2021	10:30	-32.3903	17.9038	121.42	119
C13628	CTD002	07/12/2021	16:06	-32.3898	17.9010	127.49	123
C13629	CTD003	08/12/2021	04:16	-32.3905	17.9047	122.88	122
C13630	CTD004	08/12/2021	07:03	-32.3915	17.9053	121.93	118
C13632	CTD005	08/12/2021	08:33	-32.3903	17.9022	124.34	121
C13633	CTD006	08/12/2021	10:22	-32.3922	17.9018	123.78	120
C13634	CTD007	08/12/2021	13:07	-32.3917	17.9020	124.44	121
C13635	CTD008	08/12/2021	16:08	-32.3907	17.9027	125.45	121
C13636	CTD009	08/12/2021	19:05	-32.3907	17.9042	124.36	120
C13637	CTD010	09/12/2021	03:59	-32.3905	17.9030	124.48	121
C13638	CTD011	09/12/2021	07:07	-32.3893	17.9025	125.23	122
C13639	CTD012	09/12/2021	10:04	-32.3902	17.9032	124.12	120
C13640	CTD013	09/12/2021	12:55	-32.3918	17.9035	123.75	120
C13641	CTD014	09/12/2021	15:55	-32.3912	17.9033	124.36	120
C13642	CTD015	09/12/2021	19:01	-32.3902	17.9027	125.14	120
C13643	CTD016	10/12/2021	03:59	-32.3915	17.9033	124.11	120
C13644	CTD017	10/12/2021	07:01	-32.3918	17.9052	122.67	119
C13645	CTD018	10/12/2021	10:01	-32.3905	17.9042	123.73	120
C13646	CTD019	10/12/2021	12:58	-32.3910	17.9027	123.85	121
C13647	CTD020	10/12/2021	16:01	-32.3903	17.9010	127.43	122
C13648	CTD021	10/12/2021	19:01	-32.3915	17.9025	126.3	123
C13649	CTD022	11/12/2021	04:04	-32.3902	17.9053	123.79	120
C13650	CTD023	11/12/2021	07:11	-32.3920	17.9035	123.54	119
C13651	CTD024	11/12/2021	10:01	-32.3908	17.9040	124.41	121
C13652	CTD025	11/12/2021	13:05	-32.3912	17.9028	124.99	122
C13653	CTD026	11/12/2021	16:01	-32.3933	17.9042	123.56	119
C13654	CTD027	11/12/2021	19:01	-32.3925	17.9027	124.58	120
C13655	CTD028	12/12/2021	03:58	-32.3895	17.9050	124.21	120
C13656	CTD029	12/12/2021	07:01	-32.3920	17.9040	123.92	120
C13657	CTD030	12/12/2021	10:01	-32.3912	17.9027	125.13	121
C13658	CTD031	12/12/2021	12:57	-32.3918	17.9038	124.37	121
C13659	CTD032	12/12/2021	15:59	-32.3908	17.9033	123.78	120
C13660	CTD033	12/12/2021	19:01	-32.3920	17.9042	123.75	122
C13661	CTD034	13/12/2021	03:59	-32.3910	17.9032	124.18	119
C13662	CTD035	13/12/2021	07:01	-32.3908	17.9033	124.74	123
C13663	CTD036	13/12/2021	10:01	-32.3915	17.9033	124.52	123
C13664	CTD037	13/12/2021	13:01	-32.3912	17.9037	123.79	120
C13665	CTD038	13/12/2021	16:02	-32.3905	17.9037	123.08	121
C13666	CTD039	13/12/2021	19:01	-32.3908	17.9038	124.37	121
C13667	CTD040	14/12/2021	04:02	-32.3918	17.9022	123.72	119

C13668	CTD041	14/12/2021	07:01	-32.3920	17.9037	123.46	119
C13669	CTD042	14/12/2021	10:01	-32.3913	17.9040	124.27	121
C13670	CTD043	14/12/2021	13:09	-32.3915	17.9028	124.25	120
C13671	CTD044	14/12/2021	16:01	-32.3900	17.9033	124.22	120
C13672	CTD045	14/12/2021	19:01	-32.3903	17.9033	124.37	121
C13673	CTD046	15/12/2021	04:03	-32.3905	17.9035	123.36	120
C13674	CTD047	15/12/2021	07:01	-32.3920	17.9040	122.67	120
C13675	CTD048	15/12/2021	13:01	-32.3912	17.9032	124.34	121
C13676	CTD049	15/12/2021	16:01	-32.3908	17.9032	124.04	120
C13677	CTD050	15/12/2021	19:01	-32.3908	17.9027	125.22	122
C13678	CTD051	16/12/2021	04:01	-32.3912	17.9033	123.02	119
C13679	CTD052	16/12/2021	07:01	-32.3920	17.9043	123.56	120
C13680	CTD053	16/12/2021	10:01	-32.3910	17.9040	124.49	122
C13681	CTD054	16/12/2021	13:01	-32.3915	17.9035	124.35	121
C13682	CTD055	16/12/2021	16:00	-32.3912	17.9035	124.12	121
C13683	CTD056	16/12/2021	19:01	-32.3912	17.9035	123.69	121
C13684	CTD057	17/12/2021	04:02	-32.3912	17.9038	123.85	120
C13685	CTD058	17/12/2021	10:06	-32.3900	17.9053	123.23	120
C13686	CTD059	17/12/2021	12:55	-32.3913	17.9037	124.56	121
C13687	CTD060	17/12/2021	16:33	-32.3933	17.9023	123.53	120
C13688	CTD061	17/12/2021	19:01	-32.3910	17.9030	123.06	119
C13689	CTD062	18/12/2021	04:01	-32.3915	17.9035	123.96	120

5.3.1. Preliminary results

The TS plot (Fig 5.2) shows that three water masses can be clearly differentiated: an oxygen rich warmer upper layer with slightly higher salinity, an intermediate water mass with a larger range of temperatures, and colder oxygen-poor bottom layer. A distinct warm surface layer can be observed (Fig 5.3). The contact zone between this upper and the intermediate layer forms the main thermocline, characteristic of these kind of environments. The intermediate layer presents a gradual decrease in temperature with depth until stabilizing at the bottom forming the bottom layer. An interesting feature was the ventilation or upwelling of subsurface water with temperature of $\sim 12^{\circ}\text{C}$ observed on the 17th of December.

Figure 5.2. TS plot for all CTD data obtained.

Figure 5.3. Vertical section of Temperature (ITS-90, °C) time series.

The salinity displays (Fig 5.4) the same pattern as the temperature profile, with high values in the surface water and low values at the bottom. Salinity oscillated between 34.6 and 34.9 PSU, though overall the variations was smaller than the temperature variability. Similarly, a ventilation or upwelling of cold water (temperature below 11°C) was observed in the 17th December.

Figure 5.4. Vertical section of Salinity (PSU) time series

The oxygen profile shows three distinct water masses (Fig 5.5). The upper water mass is well oxygenated with oxygen values between 5.5 and 8 ml/l, intermediate water mass with values between 3.5 and 5.0 ml/L and deep waters with values between 2.0 to 3.0 ml/L. At the thermocline the oxygen concentration decreases drastically from 4.0 to 3.5 ml/l in just a few meters. Overall, the bottom layer stays within this range of oxygen concentration. Nevertheless, it presents certain patchiness, with areas of low oxygen (dropping to 2.5 ml/l). After the 10th of December, a distinct anoxic bottom layer starts to form with concentrations between 2.0 and 2.5 ml/l. This bottom layer expanded vertically from bottom to about 50 m depth with time. Waters with oxygen levels below 4 ml/l can be seen upwelling on the 17th of December.

Figure 5.5. Vertical section of Dissolved oxygen (ml/l) time series.

The fluorometer (Fig 5.6) shows that maximum primary production was above the 20m depth, with maximums of up to 10 mg/m³. At around 20m a sharp gradient can be observed, until fluorescence fades out to 0 below approximately 20 m depth. Certain

patchiness of low fluorescence can be observed above 10 m. On the 17th December, we observed intermediate waters outcropping or upwelling that separated the observed upper surface patchiness of Fluorescence.

Figure 5.6. Vertical section of Fluorometer (mg/m³) time series.

5.4. Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP)

ADCP data were collected continuously throughout the cruise. The data collection was stopped and restarted on the 14th of December in order to provide the chief scientist with a copy of the data collected until then. The data collection was stopped when entering Table Bay. This data is to be processed after the cruise.

5.5. Ships Data System (SDS)

SDS system was started just prior to leaving the harbour and continued running throughout the cruise. The SDS server had to be rebooted on two occasions during the cruise. The first time was on the 2nd day when the meteorological data was not updating. The second time was on the 11th of December when the whole system froze. No further problems were encountered. The system was switched off once the ship had returned to Cape Town. The “save image” function on the History Graph does not work. It saves a blank image.

Figure 5.7. True wind speed timeseries.

Figure 5.8. True wind direction timeseries.

Figure 5.9. Air temperature timeseries.

Figure 5.10. Air pressure timeseries.

5.6. Surface Photosynthetically Active Radiation (SPAR)

SPAR system was started just prior to leaving the harbour and continued running throughout the cruise (Fig. 11).

Figure 5.11. Surface PAR timeseries.

5.7. Thermosalinograph (TSG)

The scientific pump feeding the TSG was turned on 15 minutes after leaving Cape Town harbour. The TSG was flushed with sea water for half an hour before data collection started. Adjustments were made to the flow rate to compensate for the PCO₂ system. A further adjustment to the flow rate was made halfway through the cruise as the water pressure to the PCO₂ system had dropped. No further adjustments were made. Data collection was stopped and restarted every morning before the first CTD cast of the day. This was done in order to allow for the previous days data to be processed onboard.

Two sections of the data raise special interested (marked with red boxes in the Fig 5.12). On the 12th through to the 13th of December strong temperature signal variations appeared, with strong oscillations of up to one degree. These strong oscillations were the result of a very shallow thermocline, starting at around 4m from the surface. The rolling of the ship, and the consequent vertical movement of the intake through the thermocline are the most plausible explanation, without any further in-depth analysis. Once the wind picked up the thermocline deepened to a depth below 10m, stabilizing the erratic temperature, as can be seen in the Fig 5.12. In order to rule out obstruction of the pump, it was cleaned in accordance with the engineering team. Other possible explanation includes the vertical oscillation of the thermocline by the effect of, e.g., a propagating internal wave.

The second data section of interest shows a sharp drop in temperature on the 17th of December. This drop is the result of an upwelling plume that was advected to the sampling station as the result of previous southerly winds. The large drop shows the front between normal surface water and cold upwelled water. The pCO₂ system

showed surface pCO₂ values of over 1000 ppm. A clear distinction of water masses can be seen before and after the front.

Figure 5.12. Temperature, Salinity, and Conductivity time series.

Fig 5.13 shows the difference between the intake and the TSG temperature sensors. Regarding the performance of the intake and the TSG sensor, no significant drift between the two sensors could be established, as is shown in the Figure 5.13 below. As expected, data segments with larger variability, such as the segment between the 12th and 13th of December that has been mentioned previously, show much larger variations between the two sensors. This is due to the time lag between the measurement while the water is pumped to the TSG. Nevertheless, the difference in segments of low variability is negligible, providing good confidence in both sensor measurements. The scientific pump was switched off and data collection was terminated prior to entering Cape Town Harbour. The scientific pump was switched off and data collection was terminated prior to entering Cape Town Harbour. The de-bubbler and TSG were then flushed with fresh water after the cruise.

Figure 5.13. Time series of the Temperature Difference: TSG -Intake

5.8. CTD Data

Data collected on the return trip from St Helena Bay to Cape Town is not included. A copy of the raw data collected during the cruise is held by the Chief Scientist. All raw and processed data will be provided to the MIMS database for storage and archiving. Further products derived from the data collected during the cruise will be shared with collaborating members of the project and registered students. All requests for access to this data must be logged with the Chief Scientist and recommended by the relevant project Principal Investigators.

5.9. Recommendations

As a result of last-minute changes to the cruise plan prior to sailing, CTD operations took place for 15 hours each day, instead of the intended 2x CTD casts per day. The daily working hours exceeded the recommended 12-hour shifts typically done by operators at sea, and creates risks, not only for the safety of the equipment, but also of the operators. For future cruises, the Chief Scientist must request 2x CTD operators, when the work to be done exceeds 12 hours per day.

The CTD bottle trigger mechanism needs to be removed and serviced/cleaned.

The syringes for the CTD need to be replaced.

The SDS server monitor needs to be replaced.

6. Biogeochemistry cruise report

Team members: *Thato Mtshali (Team Leader), Baxolele Mdokwana, Christopher Nkosinathi Jabulani, Sinalo Mswane, and Mutshutshu Tsanwani*

Report compiled by: Mr M Tsanwani and Dr Thato Mtshali

Correspondence: *mtsanwani@dffe.gov.za*

6.1. Motivation

The Benflex21 cruise took place from the 6th to 19th December 2021 along the St Helena Bay monitoring line (STBML). This region is known to be affected by the upwelling plumes of the South Atlantic central water (SACW) that are controlled by south-westerly winds. These upwelling waters are known to have high dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and macronutrients, but low in oxygen and pH. A sampling station location between station 4 and 5 of the SHBML IEP was occupied for two weeks and samples were collected from the CTD casts every 12 hours (i.e. at 6:00 am 18:00pm) and every 3 hours from the underway seawater supply pump.

6.2. General objective

The overarching objective was to collect surface seawater samples from the CTD casts and from the underway seawater supply pump for Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC), Total Alkalinity (TA), Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Nutrients, and Chlorophyll-*a* (Chl-*a*) analysis, and to measure sea surface partial pressure of carbon dioxide and dissolved oxygen underway.

6.3. Methods

During the cruise, a total number of 23 CTD casts were conducted for sub-sampling of different parameters and about 137 DO, 123 Chl-*a*, 196 macronutrients, and 196 DIC samples were collected.

6.3.1. DIC /TA measurements

Seawater samples for DIC and TA measurements were taken at 7 to 8 different depths along the water column into 8 x pre-rinsed 500ml glass bottles from the CTD casts and 1 sample from the underway pump every 3 hours. Samples were preserved by adding 100 µl of saturated Mercuric Chloride solution (Merck, SA), closed tight and stored at room temperature in the dark for further analysis in the lab ashore using the VINDTA system (Versatile INstrument for the Determination of Total inorganic carbon and Alkalinity; Marianda).

6.3.2. Chlorophyll-a concentration

About 250 ml seawater samples for Chl-a analysis were taken at 5 to 6 different depths along the water column from the Niskin bottles into 5 pre-rinsed plastic bottles and 1 sample from the underway pump every 3 hours, respectively. Chl-a samples were filtered through 0.7 μ m pore size filter paper (25mm Whatman GF/F glass fibre filter; Merck, SA) under vacuum pressure. The filter papers were folded into 2 halves, covered with aluminium foil pouches and store frozen at -80°C for further analysis ashore using a Turner Designs 10-AU fluorometer after extraction in 90% acetone.

6.3.3. Nutrients

Seawater samples for macronutrients (Nitrate, Nitrite, Silicate and Phosphate) analysis were collected in a pre-cleaned 50 ml tube. Samples were stored in a -80 freezer and will be analysed on land using Auto-Analyser.

6.3.4. Underway pCO₂

The partial pressure of carbon dioxide (pCO₂) was measured (Fig 6.1 and 6.2) using the autonomous underway pCO₂ measuring system obtainable from General Oceanics. The system is compact and operates by directing seawater flow through an equilibrator via a washable filter. The CO₂ contained in the seawater equilibrates with the gas present in the headspace gas in the equilibrator. The CO₂ in the headspace gas was pumped through a non-dispersive infrared analyser which measures CO₂ instantly. The Licor CO₂/H₂O analyser was calibrated using 4 standard gases certified to NOAA standards at regular intervals. The pCO₂ measuring system is equipped with Idronaut 315 flowcell for the measurements of pH, salinity, temperature, and dissolved oxygen. For the calibration (correction) of the sensors, underway dissolved oxygen and DIC samples were collected after 6-hour intervals.

Preliminary results indicate that the area was taking up CO₂ from the atmosphere from the time the vessel occupied the station position until the 17th of December when large amounts of CO₂ was released into the atmosphere when the seawater xCO₂ increased sharply to 1150 μ M.

Figure 6.1. Position and movement of the ship

Figure 6.2. Sea surface xCO₂ time series.

6.4. Dissolved Oxygen

The DO samples were collected into glass stoppered dissolved oxygen bottles (115 mL nominal capacity – also called “BOD bottles”) at 6 selected water column depths from the CTD cast and 1 sample from the underway pump, respectively. Sampling bottles were rinsed 3 x with seawater and filled to the brim, and then spiked immediately with 1.0 ml of Manganese (II) chloride (3.0M reagent grade MgCl₂; **reagent 1**) and Sodium hydroxide + Potassium Iodide (4.0M reagent grade NaOH + KI; **reagent 2**) solutions, respectively. A white cloudy precipitate will form, indicating

the presence of oxygen. The bottle was shaken well to homogenise the precipitate and allow it to settle for few minutes. Before titration, the sample was spiked with 2 ml concentrated Hydrochloric acid (**reagent 3**; 32% analytical grade HCl; Merck, SA), shaken well and a brown solution was formed. The solution was then titrated against Sodium Thiosulfate working solution (0.18M Na₂S₂O₃ reagent grade) by following a modified Winkler titration method (Strickland and Parsons,1968) on a pre-standardised Titrino (877 Titrino plus, ΩMetrohm; Swiss made) until the end-point was obtained. The DO bottle volume, sampling depth and concentration were recorded on a deck sheet (**Annex A**).

The DO concentration from the discrete bottle were plotted against the CTD oxygen sensor at each cast and then all DO combine (**Fig. 6.3**). Despite the few values (outliers), a good linear relationship was observed between the two measurements.

Figure 6.3. Linear plots of Winkler titration vs CTD sensor DO concentrations combined.

Underway discrete surface water DO samples were also collected and analysed using Winkler titration method. This data was compared with the underway Optode sensor connected to the pCO₂ system (**Figure 6.4**). A good linear correlation was observed.

Figure 6.4. Linear plot of Winkler titration vs pCO₂ Optode sensor.

Table 6.1: CTD and Titrino DO measurements

Station	Niskin #	Depth (m)	DO (ml/L)	Bottle #	CTD DO (ml/L)
CTD001	1	119.1	3.18	85	3.3148
	2	85.5	2.08	44	2.0995
	3	66.1	3.62	6	3.905
	4	42.1	2.36	53	2.2917
	5	19.5	5.69	9	5.85
	7	12.2	5.79	48	6.128
	CTD002	1	122.8	2.19	6
3		89.6	1.09	85	2.3067
4		69.2	2.72	44	4.217
5		48.2	1.17	53	2.2522
8		24.1	3.34	9	4.141
10		10	4.62	48	5.9241
CTD003	1	120.4	2.82	6	3.0201
	3	74.7	2.29	85	2.4309
	5	50.2	3.08	44	3.3077
	6	38.7	3.09	53	3.2994
	8	19.9	5.35	9	5.6415
	9	10.2	5.6	48	6.0391
CTD008	1	120.7	2.82	6	3.0087
	3	86.3	2.47	85	2.6007
	5	60.2	3.18	44	3.3868
	7	25.2	2.8	53	2.8517
	8	19.1	3.27	9	3.5994
	11	10	5.79	48	6.1846
CTD010	1	119.1	3	48	3.1932
	4	85.5	2.59	9	2.7439
	5	66.1	1.86	53	1.9617
	7	42.1	2.08	44	2.0939
	8	19.5	2.97	85	2.9004
	10	12.1	5.43	6	5.8816
CTD014	1	119.2	3	6	3.1893

	3	85.3	2.82	85	3.0012
	4	64.9	2.04	44	2.035
	6	29.9	2.49	53	2.5823
	8	19.9	2.96	9	3.1654
	10	13.9	5.84	48	6.4859
CTD016	1	120.5	2.69	6	2.7728
	3	98.4	3.17	85	3.3025
	4	80.2	3.2	44	3.3746
	5	52.2	3.84	53	4.2029
	8	15.2	3.68	9	3.6642
	11	10.4	5.15	48	5.9395
CTD020	1	119.7	1.97	6	1.9614
	3	95.4	3.12	85	3.1236
	4	55.8	3.65	44	3.6491
	5	31.8	3.95	53	3.9375
	6	24.6	4.08	9	4.0859
	10	8.7		48	6.2089
CTD022	1	120.1	1.78	6	1.9057
	4	65.2	2.99	44	3.222
	5	45.6	3.72	53	4.0336
	7	19.9	3.74	9	3.9734
	11	8.2	5.74	48	6.1212
CTD026	1	118.2	2.21	6	2.2685
	3	91.6	3.71	85	3.9179
	4	63.8	3.08	44	3.269
	6	30.1	3.8	53	3.997
	11	7.8	6.22	48	6.572
CTD028	1	119.4	2.23	6	2.3589
	4	75.9	3.71	85	3.9343
	5	56	3.08	44	3.2623
	6	35.3	3.82	53	4.076
	8	14.8	4.31	9	4.1431
	10	10	5.57	48	5.8239
CTD032	1	119.7	2.25	6	2.3641
???	3	84.3		85	
	5	38.9	2.16	44	4.0698
	7	19.2	5.05	53	4.161
	8	16	5.91	9	6.535
	11	8.9	6.65	48	7.426
CTD034	1	118.4	2.29	6	2.3841
	4	70	3.67	85	4.0918
	5	47.8	2.95	44	3.0604
	6	35.1	3.62	53	3.8244
	8	13.6	4.42	9	4.2478
	10	8.9	5.94	48	6.3243
CTD038	1	118.7	2.16	6	2.2364
	4	53.9	3.7	85	4.0608
	5	48.5	3.31	44	2.867
	7	29.4	3.86	53	4.0199
	8	17.9	4.28	9	4.2782
	10	11.3	7.1	48	7.4516
CTD040	1	118.1	2.29	6	2.3898

	3	75.2	2.3	85	2.3961
	5	49.3	2.83	44	2.9266
	6	34.9	3.01	53	3.1884
	8	19.7	3.21	9	3.3732
	10	15	5	49	4.6787
CTD044	1	119.5	2.3	6	2.3524
	4	71.1	2.99	85	3.0364
	5	50.7	2.99	44	3.1186
	6	36.5	2.74	53	2.7625
	8	14.3	4.2	9	4.3072
	11	10.3	6.4	48	6.6532
CTD046	1	119.4	2.3	6	2.3094
	3	61.4	3.51	85	3.1757
	4	54.9	2.71	44	2.7391
	6	24.2	2.82	53	2.8829
	8	17.9	5.04	9	5.1781
	10	11.8	5.88	48	6.0903
CTD049	1	120.1	2.2	85	2.2123
	4	65.1	3.73	44	3.7997
	5	47.8	2.96	6	3.0141
	6	28.7	2.71	53	2.6696
	7	19.9	3.04	9	3.0137
	10	13.1		48	5.4791
CTD051	1	118.9		6	2.2062
	4	75	2.22	85	2.2639
	5	39.9	3	44	3.0823
	6	30.1	2.92	53	2.9532
	7	18.7	4.99	9	5.632
	10	9.4	5.54	48	5.7214
CTD055	1	119.1	1.88	85	1.8941
	2	90.7	1.8	44	1.8053
	3	38.8	3.19	6	3.1063
	4	30.6	3.36	53	3.4597
	5	20.3	3.13	9	3.1787
	6	10.1	5.59	48	5.8399
CTD057	1	119.2	2	6	2.0354
	2	79.9	2.45	85	2.523
	3	61.9	3.2	44	3.2387
	4	39.7	4.13	53	4.1992
	6	28.4	3.75	9	3.9968
	8	10.4	5.29	48	5.5057

6.5. Future recommendations

We need to increase our CTD sampling resolution to catch full diel cycle. We also need to bring along other underway sampling instrument, such as the underway Fluorometer and a suitable underway pH sensor.

7. Eddy Covariance (ECV) Tower (mast) Cruise Report

Compiled by: Joshua Huysamen (Sea Technology Services)

Correspondence: josh@seatechnology.co.za

7.1 Pre-cruise ship work

- Mount the ECV Tower (mast) on the foredeck of the ship with the stay cables.
- Route electrical cables, water line and air-line (gas) with cable ties from the tower alongside the foredeck and into the container. Waterline hose goes to the tap on the foredeck.
- Route the electrical lines inside the container to the relevant places and plumb the gas lines to the pump and Licor gas analyser.
- The air-pump and Licor box were each secured to a wooden base and tied to the table with thin nylon rope to ensure they did not move at sea. The same for the Licor sensor setup that was on the Perspex baseplate. The laptop and multi-plug were duct-taped to the table

Eddy Covariance (ECV) Tower:

7.2. List of sensors/devices on the ECV tower

- Sonic anemometer
- Licor LI7500 CO₂/H₂O/ gas analyser for flux measurements
- Inertial motion unit (IMU) for correcting the motion of the ship
- Two Radiation sensors
- Relative Humidity and Air Temperature sensor
- Mean anemometer for mean wind speed
- Air temperature and relative humidity
- Data box which logs the data and provide power to the sensors
- GPS antenna for location and heading

7.3. List of sensors/devices in the container lab

- Laptop to receive data from the data box on the tower
- Licor LI7500 CO₂/H₂O/ gas analyser
- Air pump to pump in air from the top of the tower to the Licor sensor that is inside the container

7.8. Running the tower (sampling)

The ECV tower requires power to be on at all times and the “Logger Net” software to be connected and running on the Laptop in order to log the CR3000 logger data. The software automatically downloaded data once every 1 hour. When the tower data box power went down, the CR3000 lost data that was not downloaded to the laptop. The laptop and air-pump inside the container also needed to be powered and running 24/7. It was found that the air-pump gets quite hot, and the outer container door was left open to allow air-flow into the container to cool the motor down. The MOXA data logger logged all it’s data internally and on a USB flash disk. When the data box lost power the data was still stored on the device. Once a day it was necessary to turn on the water tap for ~1minute to clean the gas analyser sensor windows on the tower. It was also good practice to check the CR3000 logger data on the laptop for any missing values or zero readings as well as to back this up to another location. The MOXA data logger was also checked by climbing the tower partially with a safety harness and physically switching the data cable connection from the CR3000 connector to the MOXA connector. A terminal window was used to log into the MOXA and to check that data was at least logging. This Data was downloaded to the laptop via SCP when necessary to send to Brian for review.

7.9. Issues

- There were no major issues with the running of the ECV tower. It was running and sampling continuously from the first day of the cruise until the last day without any power interruptions.
- On 14/12/2021 the CR3000 data logger had some zero readings in the data but this seems to only be a problem with getting a GPS fix and the problem corrected itself once the GPS fix could be established.

7.10. Recommendations

- An air-conditioner to cool the container room with the air-pump would be necessary to use this system in worse weather conditions (e.g. Southern Ocean) because then the container door could not be left open.
- Two ethernet data cables should be used in order to connect to both data logger units in the ECV tower data box. This avoids the risk and need for someone to

physically climb the tower with a harness just to switch the cable connection every day in order to check each logger.

-

7.11. Post-cruise ship work

- The electrical cables and airline were disconnected from the container lab on the foredeck and cable ties removed. The waterline was also disconnected and removed. All of these lines were then rolled up and tied to the tower for it to be uninstalled and carried off the ship via the gangway for offloading. This requires at least 6-8 people to safely carry the tower.
- The laptop, air-pump and Licor sensor setup were uninstalled from the container and offloaded from the ship.
- The container lab was offloaded from the ship foredeck by use of a large crane.

8. Marine Top Predators Observations (Marine Mammal and Seabirds)

Observer: *Steven McCue*

Correspondence: *smseakamela@dffe.gov.za*

8.1. Introduction and methodology

The aim of this component was to record different marine mammal and seabird species associated with the waters around Benguela Air-Sea CO₂ and Heat Flux Experiment (Benflex) sampling station off St Helena. Observations were conducted daily (weather permitting) from the observation platform above the wheelhouse. The observation platform is 9.6m above sea level, therefore giving the observer a good vantage point from which to conduct the work. Activities were limited to daylight hours between 06h00 and 18h00 during the cruise dates 6th to 18th December 2021.

In line with sampling design of the Benflex cruise, a fixed-point survey approach was adopted and all observations were conducted while the vessel was stationary at the pre-determined position (Fig. 1). A search for marine mammals and seabirds covered the 360° field of view around the vessel. Secondary sighting data was collected while the vessel steamed to and from the sampling position. Various parameters were recorded; including weather, effort (e.g., start and end times) and species information. Species identification manuals were relied upon to confirm the identity of each individual sighted.

Marine mammal observations were conducted continuously whilst seabird observations were done three times in an hour. Seabird observations were conducted every 20 minutes, at 10, 30 and 50 mins past the hour. This was maintained in the absence of cetaceans which were a priority. When a cetacean was sighted, seabird observations were halted. Seabirds were individually recorded as “inflight” or “sitting on the water” at the time of the sighting, however only totals are provided in this report.

For marine mammals, a compass bearing was recorded to reduce chances of duplicate sightings. An angle board was used to determine the angle of the sighting, binoculars for species identification, and a camera (Canon 80D with a 400 mm lens) to collect pictures that aided in difficult sightings to identify at species level. Observations switched between “On-Effort” and “Off-Effort” modes, chiefly guided by weather conditions. On-Effort mode is adopted when conditions are ideal for observations. The observer switched to Off-Effort mode when sighting conditions deteriorated (e.g., >20 knots winds, rain or poor visibility). Weather data (including wind speed, direction, sea-state etc.) were recorded hourly.

8.2. Preliminary Results

8.2.1. Weather

Averages for each parameter recorded are given in Table 8.1. Weather conditions were on average conducive for observations with partly cloudy conditions. Sightability was good enough with visibility of up to 2 km, i.e. an observer could see a sighting cue (e.g., blow, breach) 2 km away, although binoculars would be required for more information on the sighting. The average wind direction was South-West (225°) with wind speeds averaging 14 kn (Fig. 8.1), leading to on average, moderate breeze, 2-meter swells and a Sea State of 4 on the Beaufort Scale.

Table 8.1. Average environmental conditions during the Benflex Cruise

Weather	Wind Direction (°)	Wind Speed(Kn)	Sea Surface Temp(°C)	Air Temp. (°C)	Visibility (nm)	Sightability	Sea state	Swell
2	225	14	16	16	2	3	4	2

Fog and wind were the only factors that affected observation effort. Work was suspended due to strong winds (i.e. >20 kn) on the 7th (11h00), 9th (16h00) and 14th (11h00) December 2021. Effort was interrupted following a late start on the 16th December 2021. Fog reduced visibility for about three hours on the 9th of December 2021. On the same day, the air temperature sensor on the SDS system was not giving a correct reading, and the ship temperature gauge was used for this day.

Figure 8.1. Average wind speed and direction for the Benflex Cruise

8.2.2. Effort

A total of 68 hours and 12 minutes was spent on active watch over the 12-day period. About 941 minutes were lost to unfavourable weather (fog and strong winds) and searching for a Slocum Glider.

8.2.3. Sightings

8.2.3.1. Marine mammal sightings

Marine mammal species observed during the cruise are listed in Table 8.2. There were 70 sightings of 4 positively identified cetacean species, and 2 unconfirmed whale sightings (one possibly a Sei whale). Humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) was sighted 53 times and had the highest individual count of approximately 180 animals, followed by dusky dolphin (*Lagenorhynchus obscurus*) which had the highest individual count of about 53 individuals from 5 sightings. The two positively identified whale species that were recorded (humpback and southern right whales) are migratory species. Humpback whales have been present in the St Helena Bay area in large numbers since October 2021 and continued to be present at the time of drafting this report. Although unconfirmed, it is not unusual to encounter a sei whales (*Balaenoptera borealis*) in coastal waters of South Africa, especially the St Helena Bay area. This offshore species has been previously encountered by Departmental Scientists in Spring/Summer months. The animal did not break the water surface but turned underwater near the vessel and surfaced about 800m further away. Based on observer experience, the size, body shape and coloration of the sighted individual was consistent with a sei whale.

Table 8.2. Marine mammal species recorded.

Species	Scientific name	Sightings	Estimate
Dusky dolphin	<i>Lagenorhynchus obscurus</i>	5	53
Heaviside's dolphin	<i>Cephalorhynchus heavisidii</i>	4	18
Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	53	180
Like Sei whale	<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>	1	1
Southern Right whale	<i>Eubalaena australis</i>	2	2
Unid Large Baleen whale		5	6
Total		70	260

8.2.3.2. Seabird sightings

Results of seabird observation effort are provided in Table 8.3. Kelp gulls (*Larus dominicanus*) were sighted 70 times with a total of 234 individual birds tallied. Common terns (*Sterna hirundo*) were second most sighted with 65 sightings; but had the highest number of individual birds (275). Other sightings included the Northern giant petrel (*Macronectes halli*) (6 animals in 6 sightings), the Long-tailed jaeger (*Stercorarius longicaudus*) (2 animals in 2 sightings) (Fig. 8.2) and Pomarine Jaeger (*Stercorarius pomarinus*) (1 animal in 1 sighting). It was also interesting to see a Common rock pigeon flying around the vessel on one occasion.

Figure 8.2: Long-tailed Jaeger (photo by S. McCue)

Table 8.3: Seabirds sighting records.

Species	Scientific name	Number	Sighting s
African Penguin	<i>Spheniscus demersus</i>	2	2
Arctic Tern	<i>Sterna paradsaea</i>	14	5
Cape Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax capensis</i>	9	4
Cape Gannet	<i>Morus capensis</i>	109	37
Common Tern	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	275	65
Cory's Shearwater	<i>Calonectris borealis</i>	6	5
Greater Crested Tern	<i>Thalasseus bergii</i>	15	14
Kelp Gull	<i>Larus dominicanus</i>	234	70
Long-tailed Jaeger	<i>Stercorarius longicaudus</i>	2	2
No birds		42	42
Northern Giant Petrel	<i>Macronectes halli</i>	6	6
Pomarine Jaeger	<i>Stercorarius pomarinus</i>	1	1
Sabine's Gull	<i>Xema sabini</i>	2	2

Sanwich Tern	<i>Thalasseus sandvicensis</i>	5	3
Shy Albatross	<i>Thalassarche cauta</i>	2	2
Sooty Sheerwater	<i>Ar denna grisea</i>	52	31
White-chinned Petrel	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	13	13
Willson's Storm Petrel	<i>Oceanites oceanicus</i>	6	6

8.3. Other work done

On request of the Chief Scientist, the observer took the responsibility of keeping an eye on the glider. (Fig. 8.3). The instrument was continuously sampling in circular pattern approximately 100m around the ship while on station and the observer informed the bridge of its position to prevent the vessel from being in its path while it is surveying the water around the vessel. The observer also had to assist by looking for the Slocum (Fig. 8.4) that would undertake 6 dive cycles per day no more than 100m upstream from the ship. The bridge was again informed of the position. Photos of the Wave glider and Slocum was also taken and given to the Chief Scientist for his record purposes. It was also requested that sea conditions be recorded photographically with the weather report that was recorded hourly to allow a visual representation of the conditions the Wave Glider and Slocum would be exposed too. The Wave Glider and Slocum also had to be retrieved with the RV Algoa's work boat. The observer, who is also an experienced skipper was requested to assist with this difficult task. All equipment was retrieved successfully.

8.4. Comments

The fixed-point survey technique was adopted for the first time during this cruise. This approach will be reviewed for the next Benflex cruise based on this experience.

Figure 8.3: Wave Glider (photo by S. McCue)

Figure 8.4: Slocum (photo by S. McCue)

9. Acknowledgements

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